

FINITE ELEMENT AIDED DESIGN OF LAMINATED AND SANDWICH PLATES USING REANALYSIS METHODS

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ABSTRACT

Recent reanalysis methods, joined with an interactive user interface, actually appear as one of the most realistic solutions to satisfy the designers of composite structures, by countering the main drawbacks of classical finite element programs (heavy input and output procedures, long computation time). As most of the classical codes are generally only analysis tools, without any efficient facilities for design, we have built the program FEAD-LASP, completely developed for the design of laminated and sandwich plates. An original reanalysis method and a specific user friendly interface have been implemented to increase the interactivity of the program.

INTRODUCTION

The classical finite element programs are not well suited to the design process which requires many repetitive studies on a same structure under different and variable conditions. In addition, the design of composite structures needs efficient facilities in order to overcome important penalties due to the materials properties and the multilayer structure.

Recent reanalysis methods joined with an interactive user interface appear as one of the most realistic solutions to satisfy the designers of composite structures by countering the above drawbacks of classical finite element programs. To achieve this goal and further provide a piece of reference software on laminated and sandwich plate design in the same manner as the reference book of Timoshenko and Woinowsky-Krieger for homogeneous and isotropic plates, we have built a specific program FEAD-LASP (Finite Element Aided Design for Laminated And Sandwich Plates), completely developed for the design of laminated and sandwich plates.

The present version, compared with the previous version of the program presented at ICCM/9 [1], introduced the "active degrees of freedom" and "definitive degrees of freedom" concepts to make this reanalysis method faster again. The principle of these concepts is to reduce matrix computation in the reanalysis method, by reducing the global set of the nodes and rigid body motions parameters to a minimal set, that completely depends on the studied structure and allows its fast resolution.

AN ORIGINAL REANALYSIS METHOD

The reanalysis method proposed by Verchery [2] permits a fast reanalysis for changes in kinematic constraints and applied forces as well, and brings a substantial gain in computation time. The kinematic constraints mean here boundary conditions, symmetry conditions, inextensibility or incompressibility constraints. Its principle is based on the fact that the rigid body motions cause the singularities of the classical equilibrium system of discrete elastic structures. The resolution for the reanalysis process is decomposed in two steps. The first step is the computation of the flexibility matrix S , which is a quasi-inverse of the stiffness matrix K :

$$S K = K S = I - R R^T. \quad (1)$$

This flexibility matrix is obtained through a regularization process, described theoretically by Verchery and numerically by Loredo [3]. Here R is the $n \times r$ matrix, the columns of which are the eigenvectors, chosen to be orthonormal, for the zero eigenvalues of the stiffness and flexibility matrices K and S . I represents the identity matrix.

The second step introduces the data relative to kinematic constraints (L , a $n \times p$ matrix), and the applied forces as well (f_d vector). The solution for the nodal displacements (u vector) can be expressed in the full form :

$$u = S (f_d - L \phi) + R \omega , \quad (2)$$

where the rigid body motions ω and reaction parameters ϕ are obtained for a discriminant system :

$$\begin{bmatrix} -L^T S L & L^T R \\ R^T L & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \phi \\ \omega \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \delta - L^T S f_d \\ R^T f_d \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

The order $p+r$ of this discriminant system is much less than the original system $K.u=f$, especially for problems with large degrees of freedom and small number of constraints. Another advantage of the method is that the reaction forces can be easily computed in the form :

$$f_r = -L. \phi. \quad (4)$$

With this method, reanalyses under various boundary conditions and loadings are made easier and faster too.

VARIANTS OF THE METHOD

We introduce here the "active degrees of freedom" and "definitive degrees of freedom" concepts that allow the previously described method to be faster again. Their principles consist of a reduction of the matrix computation, by reducing the degrees of freedom (D.O.F) and rigid body motions parameters to a minimal set that completely depends on the studied structure but that keeps sufficient information to permit the resolution.

ACTIVE DEGREES OF FREEDOM

An "active degree of freedom" represents any degree of freedom that receives either a kinematic or a loading constraint. We then obtain the necessary number of degrees of freedom to solve the discriminant system for a particular study. This number is inferior to the number n of the initial set and then most of the matrices belonging to the discriminant system can be "contracted", without loss of information. The discriminant system becomes :

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\bar{L}^T \bar{S} \bar{L} & \bar{L}^T \bar{R} \\ \bar{R}^T \bar{L} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \phi \\ \omega \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \delta - \bar{L}^T \bar{S} \bar{f}_d \\ \bar{R}^T \bar{f}_d \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

with $\bar{L} = H^T.L$, $\bar{S} = H^T.S.H$, $\bar{R} = H^T.R$, $\bar{f}_d = H^T.f_d$.

H represents here the $n \times a$ contracting matrix with $a < n$.

The \bar{S} matrix shows that only the corresponding rows or columns of S have to be computed in the regularization process. This method is very helpful to significantly reduce the computation time of the two steps of our reanalysis method.

DEFINITIVE DEGREES OF FREEDOM

The designer can eventually decide that some kinematic constraints, that correspond to a symmetry of the problem for example, stay permanent during the full design process. The corresponding degrees of freedom then become "definitive", that is to say that the corresponding rows or columns that they represent in the matrices will not be computed but eliminated in the same manner as in the classical way. The sizes of the initial matrices R , K and S will decrease and perhaps the matrix R of the rigid body motions will disappear completely. The gain of computation time is then very large but, on the other hand, no more changes can be made with the set of these "definitive" kinematic constraints.

GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF FEAD-LASP PROGRAM

To evaluate our very efficient and general reanalysis methods, which are not based on multiple automatic optimisations used in any universal finite element program but entirely piloted by the user, and further provide a piece of reference software on laminated and sandwich plate design in the same manner as the reference book of Timoshenko and Woinowsky-Krieger [4] for homogeneous and isotropic plates, we developed a specific finite element program, called FEAD-LASP (Finite Element Aided Design of Laminated And Sandwich Plates). Developed for the design of laminated and sandwich plates, this program permits both analysis and design of composite plates in linear elasticity.

This software consists of a Multiple Documents Interface (MDI) whose menu is centred around three main rubrics : input of data, resolution and results exploitation (Fig.1).

The data input begins with the geometrical definition of the structure. Rectangular composite and sandwich panels (in bending and in-plane deformations) with pre-defined regular meshes are employed which nevertheless cover a wide field of practical needs. Three new menu items are then proposed to the direct or ply by ply laminate (or sandwich) definition. Appropriate and evolutive data bases are available for this task (Fig.2). We selected a generalized stress-strain law, which describes efficiently the behaviour of both laminated plates with shear effects and sandwich plates. It takes into account all the specific features of these structures, including bending, in-plane, bending-membrane coupling with transverse shear stiffnesses (based on the extended laminated plate theory). A method for the calculation of the generalised shear stiffness, which does not require the so-called shear correction factors, has been incorporated too, for both sandwich and laminated plates [5][6].

Kinematic constraints are pre-defined for the standard cases (clamped and simply supported plates) but could be customized for particular cases. Uniform pressures, punctual loadings and natural weight, corresponding to the applied forces, can be customized as well.

The menu "solver" launches the first analysis and the possible ulterior reanalyses. The resolution is based on the reanalysis method and its variants, described in the previous sections.

Two graphic post-treatments are dedicated to the results exploitation. The first one allows the 3D visualization of the deformed structure and gives nodal information (displacements, reaction forces, strains and stresses). The second draws the displacement, strain and stress isovalues on the plate.

In view of the features nowadays provided by system environments such as Macintosh or Microsoft Windows, we developed an interface adapted to our research field, presenting similar facilities. This interface is user-friendly through the use of windows, icons, pop-up menus and dialog boxes technique. An in line hypertext help is provided, as well, to assist users who have little or no knowledge of the internal structure and methods of the program. The quasi-multitasks environment was, as much as possible, employed to keep the dialog between the software and the user and permit a communication with others codes. It thus becomes possible to quasi-simultaneously compute an analysis and visualize results of the previous one. The interactivity of the solver is principally obtained through the use of the reanalysis method and various specific routines developed to reduce the computation time.

IMPLEMENTATION OF FEAD-LASP PROGRAM

A 16-node thick plate finite element was used. It is based on a kinematic and material similarity between laminated and sandwich structures and the three dimensional finite element with two nodes in the thickness and a fictitious equivalent material with properties varying along the thickness [7]. This process applied to the finite element method allows us to use the classical finite elements in a slightly modified form and avoids resorting to special finite elements.

During the program development, a dimensional analysis, using the fact that a regular mesh was used, showed that only about 10% of the global matrix coefficients in a non-dimensional form are needed to generate the global matrix. Consequently, these quantities were computed and stored as data in the program. These data are common to all types of plates, so the assembly process is reduced to the multiplication of different data blocks by dimensional and materials properties. The analysis computational time (assembly process and solving) was compared with a classical finite element program. This comparison showed the high efficiency of the FEAD-LASP program compared with the method used in the classical finite element program.

The new reanalysis method allows both changes in the displacement boundary conditions and loads without coming back to the initial state.

The program is written in C++ object oriented language to better manage the computer system facilities. Dynamic memory allocation and resources files have been employed to manage the memory capacity in an optimal manner and permit the translation of the program into various foreign languages.

RESULTS

A study was made, concerning the comparison of the computation times for the different steps of the reanalysis method. A personal computer with a 387 arithmetic coprocessor and a 33 Mhz clock was employed for measurement.

REGULARISATION PROCESS

The number of the currently elementary operations, that corresponds to the regularization process for the FEAD-LASP program ($n=390$ D.O.F.), reaches approximately 28 million. This number corresponds to a 7 minute duration and an $O(n^3/2)$ complexity for the algorithm.

The "in place" matrix inversion algorithm, used in FEAD-LASP, is more performant than the Loredo algorithm [2], usually employed at this step, particularly when the size of the problem does not exceed 600 degrees of freedom (Fig.3). For information we remember that the algorithm of Loredo is principally based on the band shape of the K stiffness matrix, but does not consider the symmetry of the matrices. The gain is about 5 millions of operations or 1.25 minutes.

The main reason for this gain is that the symmetries of the matrices, taken into account in the algorithm of FEAD-LASP, become preponderant on the band nature of the K stiffness matrix.

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The effects of the "active" and "definitive" D.O.F are not included in this comparison. We have considered that all D.O.F were "active" and none were "definitive".

DISCRIMINANT SYSTEM AND CLASSICAL METHOD

If we use the same 16-node thick plate finite element, employed in the FEAD-LASP program, with 3 degrees of freedom per node, the difference between the number of elementary operations needed by the two resolution processes can be evaluated by the following expression :

$$\text{Difference} = \frac{1544}{3} \cdot p + 579 \cdot p \cdot m - 7636 \cdot m - 1572 \cdot m + 14976 \cdot m^2 + 12798 \cdot m^3 + 2916 \cdot m^4 - \frac{1}{6} \cdot p^3 + 144 \cdot p \cdot m^2 - \frac{9}{2} \cdot p^2 \quad (6)$$

where p represents the kinematic constraints, m the number of finite element along the edge of a square plate. The figure (Fig.4) shows the unfavorable and favorable zones for our method as compared to the classical method. We notice that the favorable zone corresponds mainly to a weak number of kinematic constraints compared to the total number of degree of freedom. The maximal computation gain, compared to the classic method, can reach two minutes for $m=6$ (800 D.O.F) and $p < 200$, with a calculation time of only 30 seconds for a reanalysis.

The effects of the "active" and "definitive" D.O.F are not included in this comparison.

REMARKS AND MATERIAL CONFIGURATION

Several micro-computers and work-stations were used to test the numerical part : it was found that personal computers as well as low cost work-stations were well suited for a fast numerical treatment, i.e. only a few minutes for the first analysis, and reanalysis in seconds. Moreover, it was seen that, even in the case of very low-cost micro-computers, the total time was reasonable in a design process. The numerical accuracy of the results agrees with other finite element codes [4] and the software has already been demonstrated [7].

To run the program satisfactorily, it is necessary to have a graphic display and an arithmetic coprocessor. The minimal required free storage capacity is about 4-Mbyte hard disc drive and 4-Mbyte RAM memory. A superior configuration is preferable and will of course provide better performances.

EXAMPLES

SANDWICH PLATE

We choose a carbon-epoxy material for the skins (*material 1*) and a glass-epoxy material for the core (*material 2*). The thickness ratio is $h_1=h_3=h/10$ for the skins and $h_2=8 \cdot h/10$ for the core.

<i>material 1 :</i>	E11=175 000 MPa	E _T =E22=E33=7 000 MPa	G12=G13=3 360 MPa
	v12=v13=v23=0.25		G23=1 400 MPa
<i>material 2 :</i>	E11=E22=280 MPa	E _T =E33=3 000 MPa	G23=G13=420 MPa
	v13=v23=0.02	v12=0.25	G12=112 MPa

The analytic solution can be written in the following form :

where E_T is the transversal stiffness modulus of the skins and L , h and w_{max} respectively the length, thickness and maximal deflection of the plate. The corresponding solution, obtained with FEAD-LASP, for a L/h ratio of 10 is $\beta=34.6$. The relative difference between our computation and the analytic solution [8] is only about 4 % in this study.

ISOTROPIC THICK PLATE

In this case, the analytic solution depends on the ratio L/h (Length/thickness) of the plate and varies between the authors. In our example, a clamped plate under a normal uniform pressure p , we compare the solution given by Srinivas and Rao [9] for $L/h=10$:

$$\frac{w_{max} \cdot D}{p \cdot L^4} \times 100 = 0.1495, \quad (8)$$

where D is the rigidity of plate bending. The corresponding solution obtained with FEAD-LASP is 0.149, which proves the FEAD-LASP capacity to solve thick plates too.

CONCLUSION

This paper has given a general description of the FEAD-LASP program and of its numerical performances. The link of pre- and post-processors (data input and output processing) with the analysis stage (finite elements) to form a design process was described and the attractive features for the user, obtained by significant reductions in computation time and user-friendly package, were emphasized.

Improvements of this program are in progress. Numerical optimisation techniques in the reanalysis method and possibilities of material changes will be incorporated.

The simplicity and the generality of the explicit reanalysis method incorporated in FEAD-LASP 2.0 allows us to anticipate a modular development of the program or the creation of new software, taking into account the geometrical variety of structures or the use of other finite elements.

REFERENCES

1. Eyraud G., Han W.S. and Verchery G., Finite Element Aided Design for Laminated and Sandwich Plates using Reanalysis Methods, Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM/9), Vol. 5, 617-624 (1993).
2. Verchery G., Régularisation du système de l'équilibre des structures élastiques discrètes, *Comptes Rendus à l'Académie des Sciences, Paris*, t. 311, Série II, 585-589 (1990).
3. Loredo A., Réanalyse de structure - Applications au contact élastique et aux matériaux incompressibles, *Thèse de doctorat (doctoral dissertation)*, Université Claude Bernard, Lyon, France (1993).
4. Timoshenko S. T. and Woinowsky-Krieger S., Theory of plates and shells, McGraw-Hill, 2nd ed. (1981).
5. Cheikh Saad Bouh A.B., Evaluation des performances de divers éléments finis et des effets d'anisotropie pour les plaques composites en flexion, *Thèse de doctorat (doctoral dissertation)*, Université Claude Bernard, Lyon, France (1992).
6. Pham Dang T. and Verchery G., Analysis of anisotropic sandwich plates assuring the continuities of displacements and transverse stresses at the interfaces", *ASME Publication* (1978).
7. Eyraud G., Han W.S. and Verchery G., Programme par éléments finis d'aide à la conception des plaques stratifiées et sandwich, *2ème Colloque National en Calcul des Structures*, Giens, France (1995).
8. Pagano N.J., Exact solution for rectangular bidirectional composites and sandwich plates and shells, *Journal of Composites Materials*, Vol. 4, 20-34 (1970).
9. Srinivas S. and Rao A.K., Flexure of thick rectangular plates, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Trans. ASME, 298-299 (1978).

Figure 1. Main menu of the FEAD-LASP software.

Figure 2 - Dialog box with a data base for the generalized stress-strain law used in FEAD-LASP

Figure 3. Comparison between the algorithm of FEAD-LASP and Loredo (bis 390 D.O.F)

Figure 4 - Favorable and defavorable zones for the FEAD-LASP reanalysis method compared to the classical method (at the iterative process)